

***Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy analysis of an adsorption
process with a coupled preceding chemical step***

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ABSTRACT

The impedance equations for the case of an adsorption process including a preceding homogeneous chemical step have been derived and compared to the corresponding equations for the case of a pure adsorption process. They involve behaviours with the frequency that differ from those of the impedance equations for a pure adsorption process. However, two limiting cases have been deduced in which the frequency behaviour of the impedance cannot be distinguished from the case of an adsorption process without any chemical step: the *high frequency* and the *low frequency* limits that hold for low and high values of the rate constant of the chemical reaction, respectively.

The analysis as a function of the frequency is discussed on the basis of the complex frequency-normalized admittance plots and also based on the frequency dependence of the real and imaginary frequency-normalized admittance components. The influence of the values of the equilibrium and the rate constants of the chemical step is discussed for different adsorption kinetic regimes. In this way the conditions for detecting the chemical step are delimited and suitable analysis are proposed to obtain the adsorption parameters and the characteristic constants of the chemical step.

The analysis is applied as an example, to the impedance of adenine adsorption on Au(111) electrodes from acidic solutions at a representative electrode potential. It is proved that the low frequency limit applies and the equilibrium constant for the chemical step is obtained.

Keywords: EIS; adsorption kinetics; homogenous coupled reactions; gold electrodes

1.- INTRODUCTION

It has frequently been observed in the study of electrochemical process that the electroactive species that undergo an electron transfer are also involved in chemical reactions in solution that are named as "homogeneous reactions". Therefore, the concentration profiles of electroactive species are altered and it is necessary to take into account the chemical reaction in the equations of the flux of the species towards or from the electrode. One of these cases takes place when the electroactive species is not initially present in solution but it is generated in the chemical reaction, which is so named as the "preceding chemical reaction" and the corresponding mechanism as the CE mechanism. A chemical adsorption process on an electrode is similar, in some ways, to an electron transfer process, as some charge is transferred to or from the electrode due to the chemical interaction between the metal and the adsorbate. Many electrode adsorption processes of organic compounds are known to be affected by chemical reactions, specially by protonation/deprotonation equilibriums [1–9]. That is the case, for instance, with adenine adsorption on gold electrodes from acidic solutions for which the IR-spectro-electrochemical studies has shown that the species that get adsorbed is the deprotonated form, even at pH values long below the pK_a of the adenine form that is present in solution [10].

The adsorption of biologically relevant molecules on metal electrodes is of great interest in relation to the understanding of the respective biological roles and also for technical applications such as biosensors and drug delivery platforms fabrication. Although significant advances concerning the molecular interpretation of the adsorption on solid metal electrodes have been reached nowadays by application of spectro-electrochemical and nanoscopic techniques, the kinetics of the adsorption has been scarcely addressed. The Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) technique and

the use of single crystal electrodes with well-defined surfaces, are suitable tools to study the kinetics of adsorption and so we have applied them to study the kinetics of adenine adsorption on Au(111) electrodes from solutions of several pH values, ranging from 1 to 12 [11,12].

The first adsorption kinetic models were reported by Dolin and Ershler for the limiting case of kinetic control only by the activation step, [13], and by Frumkin and Melik-Gaykazyan for the case of an adsorption process in which the kinetic control only takes place by diffusion, [14]. Both limiting cases were later combined, and the adsorption impedance equations for a general kinetic control were derived by Sluyters-Rehbach and Sluyters, [15,16]. The derivation developed later by Kerner and Pajkossy, based on the same principles [17], allows a more clear identification of the physical meaning of the impedance parameters involved in the model, and also the splitting of the net rate of absorption (or desorption) on a proper rate constant and on a surface excess depending function, related to the adsorption isotherm.

In this paper, the impedance equations for an electrochemical adsorption process that is preceded by a chemical homogeneous reaction are derived, following the development in reference [17]. To derive the impedance equations in this work, the chemical reaction has now been included in the flux equations of the species that can adsorb on the electrode. The frequency dependence of the impedance or admittance equations is analysed in comparison to the case of an adsorption process with only diffusional mass transport, without coupled homogeneous kinetics. As an example, the analysis is applied to adenine adsorption on Au(111) electrodes from 0.1M HClO₄ solutions at a representative adsorption potential, in order to detect electrochemical evidences of the chemical reaction that according to the previous IR spectroelectrochemical results is preceding the adsorption process.

2.- THEORY

An adsorption process including a preceding first order chemical step can be represented as in scheme 1:

- scheme 1 -

The rate of the chemical step is formulated as:

$$v_{chem} = \frac{d c_B}{d t} = k_1 c_B - k_{-1} c_A \quad (1)$$

where k_1 and k_{-1} are the forward and backward rate constants of the preceding chemical step and c_B and c_A are the concentrations of species B and A, respectively.

For the adsorption step the Frumkin and Melik-Gaykazyan adsorption kinetics model [14] was adopted, following further modifications that do not require any "a priori" assumption concerning the type of isotherm or the potential dependence of the adsorption and desorption rate constants [16,17]. According to them, the rate of the adsorption can be formulated as:

$$v_{ad} = \frac{d \Gamma_A}{d t} = k_{ad} f_{ad}(\Gamma_A) c_{A,x=0} - k_d f_d(\Gamma_A) \quad (2)$$

where k_{ad} and k_d are the potential dependent adsorption and desorption rate constants; Γ_A is the surface excess of species A; and $f_{ad}(\Gamma_A)$ and $f_d(\Gamma_A)$ are monotonic functions of the surface excess with values between 0 and 1. $f_{ad}(\Gamma_A)$ tends to 0 and $f_d(\Gamma_A)$ tends to 1 as the surface excess tends to its maximum value. The explicit expressions of $f_{ad}(\Gamma_A)$ and $f_d(\Gamma_A)$ depend on the specific isotherm that applies to the adsorption process.

The adsorption rate, $v_{ad} = v_{ad}(\Gamma_A, c_A, E)$ is a function of three interdependent variables: the surface excess and the concentration of A at the electrode surface ($x=0$), and the applied potential, E. On the other hand, for a small amplitude ac potential perturbation a linear approximation can be considered applicable [16] so, the total change in the adsorption rate that results, Δv_{ad} , can be expressed as a function of the changes in the three variables, ΔE , $\Delta \Gamma$ and $\Delta c_{A,x=0}$, which in the Laplace's transformation domain can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\Delta v_{ad}) &= \overline{\Delta v_{ad}} \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial v_{ad}}{\partial E} \right)_{\Gamma_A, c_A} \overline{\Delta E} + \left(\frac{\partial v_{ad}}{\partial \Gamma_A} \right)_{E, c_A} \overline{\Delta \Gamma_A} + \left(\frac{\partial v_{ad}}{\partial c_{A,x=0}} \right)_{E, \Gamma_A} \overline{\Delta c_{A,x=0}} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Evidently, $\Delta c_{A,x=0}$ must be related to the changes in the concentration of c_B , Δc_B , and both changes in the Laplace's domain can be expressed as functions of the changes in the adsorption rate, $\overline{\Delta v_{ad}}$, as deduced in the Appendix for $\overline{\Delta c_{A,x=0}}$, equation (A7). On the other hand, Laplace transformation of equation (2) provides the relation between $\overline{\Delta \Gamma_A}$ and $\overline{\Delta v_{ad}}$:

$$\overline{\Delta \Gamma_A} = s^{-1} \overline{\Delta v_{ad}} \quad (4)$$

where s is defined as $s = \omega i$ with $i = \sqrt{-1}$.

The adsorption impedance, Z_{ad} , is defined as the ratio of the changes in the Laplace domain of the potential and of the current density due to the adsorption:

$$Z_{ad} = \frac{\overline{\Delta E}}{\overline{\Delta I_{ad}}} \quad (5)$$

where the current density of adsorption is defined as:

$$I_{ad} = \left(\frac{\partial \sigma^M}{\partial \Gamma_A} \right)_E \frac{d \Gamma_A}{d t} = \left(\frac{\partial \sigma^M}{\partial \Gamma_A} \right)_E v_{ad} \quad (6)$$

with σ^M being the charge density on the metal.

Substitution of equations (A7) and (4) into equation (3) allows the derivation of the expression for the adsorption impedance defined in equation. (5), as:

$$Z_{ad} = R_{ad} + \sigma_{ad} G(s) + (C_{ad} s)^{-1} \quad (7)$$

where $G(s)$ is given by the same expression deduced for an electron transfer process coupled to a preceding homogeneous chemical step, named Gerischer impedance [16,18–20]:

$$G(s) = \left[\frac{K_c}{K_c + 1} s^{-\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{K_c + 1} (s + k_c)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right] \quad (8)$$

with $K_c = k_1/k_{-1}$ being the equilibrium constant of the chemical step and $k_c = k_1 +$

k_{-1} is the global rate constant (addition of the forward and backward rate constants) for the chemical step.

The frequency independent parameters R_{ad} , σ_{ad} and C_{ad} are the adsorption resistance, the adsorption Warburg coefficient and the adsorption capacitance, respectively. Their definitions are the same that in the impedance model for the adsorption kinetics in the absence of coupled chemistry [16,17], :

$$R_{ad}^{-1} = \left(\frac{\partial v_{ads}}{\partial E} \right)_{\Gamma_A, c_A} \left(\frac{\partial \sigma^M}{\partial \Gamma_A} \right)_E \quad (9a)$$

$$\sigma_{ad} = R_{ad} \left(\frac{\partial v_{ad}}{\partial c_A} \right)_{E, \Gamma_A} D^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (9b)$$

$$C_{ad}^{-1} = -R_{ad} \left(\frac{\partial v_{ad}}{\partial \Gamma_A} \right)_{E, c_A} \quad (9c)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient of A species.

Evidently, R_{ad} , σ_{ad} and C_{ad} are potential-dependent parameters as the partial derivatives that are included in their definitions depend on the potential.

The interfacial impedance has also to account for the charging of the double layer at constant surface excess, which provides a double layer current density, I_{dl} :

$$I_{dl} = \left(\frac{\partial \sigma^M}{\partial E} \right)_{\Gamma_A} \frac{dE}{dt} = C_{dl, \Gamma_A} \frac{dE}{dt} \quad (10)$$

The double layer current density is additive to the adsorption current density, so a double layer impedance Z_{dl} , can be easily deduced from equation (10), which is in parallel with the adsorption impedance:

$$Z_{dl} = (C_{dl, \Gamma_A} s)^{-1} \quad (11)$$

Therefore, the electrode impedance becomes the combination of the adsorption and the double layer impedances as:

$$Z_{el} = \{ [R_{ad} + \sigma_{ad} G(s) + (C_{ad} s)^{-1}]^{-1} + C_{dl, \Gamma_A} s \}^{-1} \quad (12)$$

Equation (12) provides the general expression for the interfacial impedance of an adsorption process coupled to a chemical step previous to the adsorption step. The influence of the preceding chemical step in the frequency dependence of the adsorption impedance is confined to the term that includes $G(s)$ in equation (12).

The expression deduced for the adsorption process in the absence of coupled chemistry can be obtained from the general expression with $G(s) = s^{-1/2}$. This situation

corresponds to the trivial case when the equilibrium constant of the chemical step is very high ($K_c \gg 1$).

Apart from this trivial case, two limiting cases can be distinguished depending on the relative values of s and k_c .

In the *high frequency limit*, that applies when $s \gg k_c$, the function $G(s)$ simplifies to $s^{-1/2}$. Therefore, the adsorption impedance has the same frequency dependence than in the absence of the previous chemical step:

$$(Z_{ad})^{HF} = R_{ad} + \sigma_{ad}s^{-1/2} + (C_{ad}s)^{-1} \quad (13)$$

In the *low frequency limit*, when $s \ll k_c$, it is possible to simplify $G(s)$ expression so the adsorption impedance becomes:

$$(Z_{ad})^{LF} = R_{ad} + \sigma_{ad} \frac{k_c^{-1/2}}{K_c + 1} + \sigma_{ad} \frac{K_c}{K_c + 1} s^{-1/2} + (C_{ad}s)^{-1} \quad (14)$$

This equation provides the same frequency dependence than equation (13) but with an apparent Warburg coefficient that includes the true Warburg coefficient and the equilibrium constant of the chemical step:

$$\sigma_{ad}^{app} = \sigma_{ad} \frac{K_c}{K_c + 1} \quad (15a)$$

and an apparent adsorption resistance that includes in addition to the true adsorption resistance, the equilibrium and the rate constants of the chemical step, according to:

$$R_{ad}^{app} = R_{ad} + \sigma_{ad} \frac{k_c^{-1/2}}{K_c + 1} \quad (15b)$$

Focusing on the previous chemical equilibrium, the *high frequency* and the *low frequency limits* correspond to non-labile and labile equilibria, respectively.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

The working solutions were prepared with ultrapure water freshly dispensed by a MilliQ system, suprapure electrolyte reagents (HClO₄, NaF) and adenine (Sigma-Aldrich®).

A three electrode cell was used, with a gold Au(111) single crystal acting as working electrode, prepared according to the Clavilier method [21]. It was flame annealed just before it contacted with the working solution by the meniscus method. A gold wire was used as auxiliary electrode and a Hg/Hg₂SO_{4(s)}/K₂SO_{4(sat)} was the reference electrode, contacted to the working solution through a salt bridge to avoid contamination of the cell.

The impedance measurements were obtained with an IviumStat, from Ivium Technologies, in a range of frequencies from 20 to 7500 Hz and an ac amplitude perturbation of 10 mV. The measurement procedure, already described elsewhere [12,22], was designed to avoid the effects of the electrochemical reconstruction/ lifting of the reconstruction on the impedance spectra obtained.

4.- DISCUSSION

4.1.- Frequency analysis of the Gerischer impedance, $G(s)$

The contribution of the preceding chemical step to the frequency dependence of the impedance spectra is analysed in the complex plane representation of the function $G(\omega)$ for different combinations of the reaction parameters K_c and k_c . In Figure 1 some

representative curves are generated in the frequency range from 0.1 Hz to 10 kHz. The behaviour in the absence of a preceding chemical step (coincident with the trivial case when $G(\omega) = (i \omega)^{-1/2}$) corresponds to the bisector in Fig.1 (the straight line with slope 1). It is reached for high K_c values (over 100) independently on the rate constant value, k_c , in all the frequency range. The *low frequency limit* shows up as straight lines, parallel to the bisector line in the low frequency range. This limit holds in a range of low frequencies that depends on the K_c and k_c values (see lines 2 and 3 for $K_c = 1$ and lines 5 and 6 for $K_c = 0.1$ in Fig. 1). On the other hand, the *high frequency limit* shows up as straight lines coincident with the bisector in a limited range of high frequency values, depending on the K_c value (see line 4 for $K_c = 1$ and line 7 for $K_c = 0.1$ in Fig.1). The transition between both limiting cases can be clearly observed at ω values in the frequency range of $10^{-1} k_c - 10 k_c$ for K_c values lower than 10.

--- figure 1----

4.2.- Frequency analysis of the electrode admittance

In the kinetic study of an adsorption process three different adsorption kinetic situations have been considered [16,17]: mixed kinetic control by activation of the adsorption and by diffusion, kinetic control exerted mainly by diffusion and kinetic control exerted mainly by adsorption activation. Those kinetic regimes are characterised by the relative values of the relaxation times of diffusion and of adsorption, τ_D and τ_H respectively, that are related to the values of R_{ad} , σ_{ad} and C_{ad} [16]:

$$\tau_D^{1/2} = -\frac{\left(\frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial c}\right)_E}{(2D)^{1/2}} = 2^{-1/2} \sigma_{ad} C_{ad} \quad (16a)$$

$$\tau_H = \left(\frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial v}\right)_{E,c} = R_{ad} C_{ad} \quad (16b)$$

Kerner and Pajkossy[17] showed that for a single adsorption step a clear picture of the kinetic regime can be visualized by the complex plane plot of the interfacial frequency-normalized admittance, also termed ‘interfacial capacitance’, that can be calculated from the cell impedance after correction of the solution resistance, R_s as:

$$C(\omega) = \frac{Y_{el}(\omega)}{\omega} = \frac{1}{\omega (Z_{cell}(\omega) - R_s)} \quad (17)$$

In the absence of coupled chemical reactions the plot of the real component of the interfacial capacitance, $(Y'_{el} \omega^{-1})$, vs its imaginary component, $(Y''_{el} \omega^{-1})$, must be close to a circular arc. At high frequencies the intercept of the arc with the abscises axis provides the value of C_{dl,Γ_A} , while the intercept at low frequencies correspond to the $(C_{dl,\Gamma_A} + C_{ad})$ magnitude. If the adsorption step is slow as compared to the diffusion, $\tau_H \geq 10 \tau_D$, the circular arc in the complex interfacial capacitance plot becomes a perfect semicircle with the centre located on the abscises axis. On the contrary, when the kinetic control is due mainly to diffusion, $\tau_D \geq 10 \tau_H$, a ‘depressed’ circular arc is obtained, with the centre located below the abscises axis. In the case of a mixed control by diffusion and adsorption activation, the arc observed is deformed, approaching to the perfect semicircle at higher frequencies and to the depressed semicircle at lower frequencies.

In Figure 2 the frequency dependence of the interfacial capacitance for the adsorption process with a preceding chemical step is illustrated in the complex plot representation of the "interfacial capacitance", Y'_{el}/ω vs Y''_{el}/ω . For the generation of the theoretical impedance spectrums typical capacitance values have been used: $C_{dl,\Gamma_A} = 20 \mu F cm^{-2}$ and $C_{ad} = 150 \mu F cm^{-2}$. Then, the τ_D and τ_H values have been suitably selected in order to simulate the different kinetic control regimes and the respective R_{ad} and σ_{ad}

values are calculated with equations (16) and the selected τ_D and τ_H values for every regime. In Figure 2a the influence of the K_c and k_c values (the same values as in Figure 1 have been chosen) on an adsorption process under kinetic control by diffusion ($\tau_D = 1$ ms, $\tau_H = 0.1$ ms) is illustrated. In Figures 2b and 2c the cases of a mixed kinetic control ($\tau_D = 1$ ms, $\tau_H = 1$ ms) and of a kinetic control by adsorption activation ($\tau_D = 1$ ms, $\tau_H = 10$ ms) are respectively presented.

-- Figures 2 a, b and c--

In Figure 2a, the case of adsorption in the absence of the chemical reaction provides as expected a "depressed" circular arc. The curves for the adsorption process with a preceding coupled chemical reaction tend to coincide at high frequencies with the depressed circular arc representing the pure adsorption process, so the *high frequency limit* can be clearly distinguished. The curves for most of the K_c and k_c combinations treated in Figure 2a present the *high frequency limit* only at frequencies higher than 1kHz, but in curves 4 and 7 this limiting case extend till around 20 Hz, so in these cases experiments at very low frequencies (lower than 20 Hz) are required in order to get information about the chemical reaction. On the contrary, any of the curves seem to fit the *low frequency limiting* curves, generated with the respective K_c values and a very high k_c value (10^7 s⁻¹) and represented with filled circles in Fig 2, in a reasonable range of frequencies. In fact, all the curves except curves 4 and 7 clearly show separation from the pure adsorption case, exhibiting a different trend at high frequencies ("depressed" semicircles) and at low frequency values ("distorted" semicircles). Therefore, the presence of a chemical reaction can be clearly inferred from the complex interfacial capacitance plots. In the case of mixed kinetic control (Figure 2b) the "distorted" semicircle for the pure adsorption can change towards a perfect semicircle when a

preceding chemical reaction with a low K_c value takes place. The distortion of the semicircle changes significantly with the k_c values, being observed at high frequencies for low k_c values (close to the adsorption in the absence of the chemical reaction) or at low frequencies for high k_c values (close to *the low frequency limit* case). However, in the case of kinetic control by adsorption activation (Figure 2c) the curves for the pure adsorption process and for the one with a preceding chemical step are close to perfect semicircles, so the complex interfacial capacitance plots are less sensitive to the kinetic parameter of the preceding reaction. The plots corresponding to the *high* and *low frequency limiting cases* become closer as the kinetic control by the activation of the adsorption becomes more relevant.

4.3.-Evaluation of the adsorption and the reaction parameters

The complex interfacial capacitance plots are useful as diagnostic criteria of the type of adsorption process, with or without a coupled chemical reaction. However, the plots of the real and imaginary components of the interfacial capacitance as a function of the frequency (or $\omega^{-1/2}$) are more sensitive to the influence of the adsorption and reaction parameters. Therefore, for the evaluation of the four characteristic adsorption parameters (R_{ad} , σ_{ad} , C_{ad} and C_{dl,Γ_A}) and the equilibrium and rate constants of the chemical reaction, it is convenient to analyze the real and imaginary components of the interfacial capacitance as a function of the frequency. Some typical plots of the real component, $(Y'_{el} \omega^{-1})$ and of the imaginary component, $(Y''_{el} \omega^{-1})$ as functions of $\omega^{-1/2}$ are given in Figures 3a and 3b, respectively, for the case of kinetic control by diffusion and the same set of parameters as in Fig 2a. It can be observed that the presence of the chemical reaction generates quite different plots. The differences are especially significant in the plots corresponding to the real component as they can show

asymmetric peaks for low values of the equilibrium constant of the chemical step. The peak shifts towards higher frequency values and it becomes narrower as k_c becomes higher. The peaks are higher and their dependence on the k_c values are more significant for lower K_c values. The plots of the imaginary component are sigmoid curves that tend to reach the value of C_{dl,r_A} at high frequencies and the value of $(C_{dl,r_A} + C_{ad})$ at low frequencies.

---Fig 3a and 3b -----

Evidently, the analysis of the real and imaginary interfacial capacitance components as a function of the frequency is sensitive also to the combination of the R_{ad} and σ_{ad} values. In order to illustrate the effect of the four frequency-independent adsorption parameters, two sets of the four parameters have been selected to simulate two adsorption cases. The value of R_{ad} is four time higher in one set (lines in blue) than in the other set (lines in pink). The sets of adsorption parameters values imply also two sets of τ_D and of τ_H values, both corresponding to mixed kinetic control. In the generation of the curves for the case of adsorption with a preceding chemical step the value $K_c = 0.01$ was adopted as an example and two values of k_c (1000 s^{-1} and 100 s^{-1}) have been considered. In Figure 4 the corresponding complex interfacial capacitance plots are given, while in Figures 5a and 5b the plots of the real and imaginary interfacial capacitance components as a function of the inverse of the frequency are respectively shown.

Fig. 4

The complex interfacial capacitance plots in figure 4 corresponding to the adsorption with a preceding chemical step clearly show the deviation from the plots of adsorption without any chemical step (or *high frequency limit*) and from the *low frequency limit* curves that will be expected according to equation (14) and $K_c = 0.01$ and $k_c = 1000 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (represented as crosses). The deviation from the *low frequency* case of the curves obtained with the high k_c value (1000 s^{-1}) is more significant in the set corresponding to the lower R_{ad} value, while the deviation from the *high frequency limit* of the curves with the lower k_c value (100 s^{-1}) is more visible in the set with higher R_{ad} value.

Figs. 5a and 5b

The peaks in the $(Y'_{el} \omega^{-1})$ vs $\omega^{-1/2}$ plots (Fig 5a) shift towards lower frequencies and become wider as R_{ad} increases, but the same influence of the k_c values on the frequency and width of the peak already commented is maintained irrespective of the set of adsorption values. The *low frequency* limiting cases appear as curves with narrower and higher peaks, shifted towards higher frequencies. The curve for the higher k_c value (1000 s^{-1}) is very close to the curve for the *low frequency limit* generated with equation (14) only in the case of the set with a high R_{ad} value. In the set with a low R_{ad} value the two curves are clearly different at frequency values around the peak. However, the curves with the lower k_c value differ more from the *high frequency* limit curves in the case of the set with the higher R_{ad} value. Although the $(Y''_{el} \omega^{-1})$ vs $\omega^{-1/2}$ are less sensitive to the R_{ad} and k_c values, the same tendency is observed regarding the applicability of the low and the high frequency cases. The curves of the imaginary components clearly tend at low frequency values to the corresponding $(C_{dl,\Gamma_A} + C_{ad})$ values.

4.4.-Example: the adsorption of adenine on Au(111) electrodes from acid solutions.

The studies about the adsorption of adenine on Au(111) electrodes from 0.1 M HClO₄ by voltammetry and in-situ Fourier transform infrared reflection absorption spectroscopy [10,23,24] have concluded that the neutral adenine form (AdH₃) is the species which can chemically get adsorbed on the electrode, so the cationic adenine form, (AdH₄⁺) that exists in the bulk of acidic solutions (adenine pK_{a1} = 4.2) has to get deprotonated in a step preceding the adsorption step, according to the mechanism in scheme 2.

--- scheme2----

In previous works the adsorption kinetics of adenine on Au(111) electrodes has been studied at pH values 1, 7.5 and 12 by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy [11,12]. In all these cases the experimental frequency dependence is formally identical to the one corresponding to an adsorption process without any preceding chemical step, as expressed in equation (13). However, according to the IR-spectroelectrochemical results obtained from solutions at pH 1 and at pH 7.5, in the case of adsorption from solutions at pH 1 this frequency dependence must result because either the *high frequency limiting case* or the *low frequency limiting case* for the adsorption model including a preceding deprotonation reaction must hold. In that case, the concentration of H⁺ ions (0.1 M) is much higher than the concentration of adenine (1mM), so the backward chemical step can be considered as a pseudo-first order process with an apparent rate constant that includes the concentration of H⁺ ions. The sum of the rate constants of a protonation/deprotonation step must be high, of the same order of magnitude that the molecular vibrational frequencies (10¹²-10¹⁴ s⁻¹), much higher than the upper limit of the frequency range used in the measurements (7500 Hz). Therefore the *low frequency limiting case* is likely to hold in the adsorption of adenine at pH 1. In Figure 6 the experimental complex interfacial capacitance plot obtained at a representative potential

(the potential of the maximum in the pseudocapacitance-potential plot) is shown. It is a slightly distorted (at high frequencies) and depressed (at low frequencies) arc that can be considered as originated by a mixed kinetic controlled adsorption process without any chemical step. Apparently, when the experimental arc is compared to the arcs in Fig 2b for the case of a mixed kinetic controlled adsorption process, there is not any indication of the deprotonation step.

The data of the real and imaginary interfacial capacitance components have been plotted in Figure 7 in the form of $(Y'_{el} \omega^{-1})$ (Fig 7a) and $(Y''_{el} \omega^{-1})$ (Fig. 7b) as functions of $\omega^{-1/2}$. The real component plot shows a characteristic asymmetric peak. The interfacial capacitance component functions of $\omega^{-1/2}$ can be used for a separate fitting analysis to the corresponding theoretical equations (eq (13) or eq (14)) in order to obtain the four adsorption parameters. The real component of the function depends only of three of them, R_{ad} , σ_{ad} and C_{ad} while the imaginary component is more sensitive to the C_{ad} and C_{dl,Γ_A} values, so the separate fitting to both functions, using as starting parameters for C_{ad} and C_{dl,Γ_A} the high and low frequency limits of $(Y''_{el} \omega^{-1})$ can be very useful, provided the parameters obtained from the analysis of each component are the same within the experimental errors, as it is the case in the analysis of the experimental data at pH 1. Moreover, a simultaneous fitting with the frequency of both components of the interfacial capacitance according to either equation (13) or (14) was conducted, with unitary weighting, with the same results than the separate analysis to each interfacial capacitance component. Satisfactory fittings to the limiting cases equations were observed with the set of parameters: $R_{ad} = 0.41 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$, $\sigma_{ad} = 81 \Omega \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1/2}$, $C_{ad} = 165 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$ and $C_{dl,\Gamma} = 10 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$. In Figures 6 and 7 the curves generated with these parameters and equations (13) or (14) indicate good agreement with the two frequency limiting cases. However, the low value obtained for σ_{ad} as compared to the σ_{ad}

obtained from solutions of pH 7.5 at the corresponding potential of the maximum in the pseudo-capacitance-potential curve (minimum in the σ_{ad} - E curve), which is $370 \Omega \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ [11], is a clear indication of the chemical reaction, and of the applicability of the *low frequency* limiting case. Therefore, the value of the equilibrium constant for the chemical step, K_c , can be obtained from the ratio between the σ_{ad} values at the two pH values, according to equation (15a). In this way the value for K_c was estimated to be 0.3. On the contrary, the R_{ad} values obtained at pH 1 do not provide any information about the rate constant of the chemical step due to its high value that annuls the second summation in equation. (15b).

In Figure 7, the curves of the real and imaginary components as a function of the frequency are also plotted in the form of Y'_{el} vs ω (Fig. 7c) and of Y''_{el} vs ω (Fig.7d). Usually, these functions are used in the fitting to the theoretical equations in order to obtain the adsorption parameters, however, they do not show any significant feature and are less sensitive to the parameters than the $(Y'_{el} \omega^{-1})$ vs $\omega^{-1/2}$ and $(Y''_{el} \omega^{-1})$ vs $\omega^{-1/2}$ forms proposed in this paper.

--Fig 6--

--Fig 7--

In Figs 6 and 7 the plots generated with equation (13) for the high frequency limiting case (or adsorption process without a preceding chemical step) and the σ_{ad} value obtained at pH 7.5 taken as “true” value are also shown for comparison. The real interfacial capacitance component plots for this case do not show the representative peak, and the generated complex interfacial capacitance plot is clearly different from the experimental plot; it is a suppressed semi-circle, as corresponding to an adsorption process kinetically controlled by diffusion.

CONCLUSIONS

The impedance equations for an adsorption process that includes a preceding chemical step imply in many situations a frequency dependence that differs from the case of the pure adsorption process. The differences depend on the value of the equilibrium constant of the chemical step, K_c . This value should be lower than 100 in order to detect the different behaviours. However, even with low K_c values, two limiting cases provide the same frequency dependence than the pure adsorption process: the *high frequency* and the *low frequency* limits that can be obtained with low or high values for the rate constant of the chemical step, k_c , respectively. The high frequency limit does not provide any information concerning the chemical step, but the low frequency limit includes K_c and k_c in apparent Warburg and adsorption resistance parameters.

The complex interfacial capacitance plots are very useful in order to detect the presence of the chemical step as they may change from the expected semicircles, "depressed" semicircles or "distorted" semicircles for the pure adsorption process. The differences are more significant in the case of diffusion or mixed kinetic control of the adsorption step.

However, in order to obtain the adsorption parameters and the equilibrium and rate constants of the chemical step the analysis of the real and imaginary components of the interfacial capacitance as a function of the frequency is recommended. The $(Y'_{el} \omega^{-1})$ vs $\omega^{-1/2}$ plots show characteristic asymmetric peaks that greatly depend on the k_c values, becoming narrower, higher and shifted towards higher frequencies as k_c increases. The differences are more visible for lower K_c values. The corresponding plots of the imaginary components, $(Y''_{el} \omega^{-1})$ vs $\omega^{-1/2}$ are sigmoid curves that provide the capacitance values C_{dl,Γ_A} and $(C_{dl,\Gamma_A} + C_{ad})$ at high and low frequencies, respectively.

In addition, both the complex interfacial capacitance plots and the interfacial capacitance component as a function of the frequency plots depend on the adsorption resistance, R_{ad} . Adsorption processes with lower R_{ad} values provide curves that are more sensitive to the chemical reaction parameters.

The experimental complex interfacial capacitance plot obtained at a representative potential for adenine adsorption on Au(111) electrodes from 0.1M HClO₄ solutions shows a frequency behaviour identical to the case of a pure adsorption process. The real interfacial capacitance component data can be fitted to the low frequency case providing apparent Warburg coefficient. The comparison of these values to the corresponding Warburg coefficient obtained for the adsorption from neutral solutions where the chemical step is absent, allows us to obtain the equilibrium constant for the chemical step in acid solutions.

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Appendix

The impedance model for an adsorption process including a preceding homogeneous chemical step can be derived using the same procedure as for a faradaic reaction with a previous chemical step (CE mechanism) [18–20]. The solution concentrations of the species A and B in scheme 1 obey the second law of Fick and include the rate of the chemical step. For linear diffusion, with D being the common diffusion coefficient of A and B:

$$\frac{\partial c_B}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 c_B}{\partial x^2} - k_1 c_B + k_{-1} c_A \quad (\text{A1a})$$

$$\frac{\partial c_A}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 c_A}{\partial x^2} + k_1 c_B - k_{-1} c_A \quad (\text{A1b})$$

Equations (A1) can be transformed into equations (A3) with the change of variables:

$$c_P = c_B + c_A \quad (\text{A2a})$$

$$c_Q = K_c c_B - c_A \quad (\text{A2b})$$

So, that:

$$\frac{\partial c_P}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 c_P}{\partial x^2} \quad (\text{A3a})$$

$$\frac{\partial c_Q}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 c_Q}{\partial x^2} - k_c c_Q \quad (\text{A3b})$$

That in the Laplace's domain become:

$$s \bar{c}_P - c_{P,t=0} = \frac{\partial^2 \bar{c}_P}{\partial x^2} \quad (\text{A4a})$$

$$s \bar{c}_Q - c_{Q,t=0} = \frac{\partial^2 \bar{c}_Q}{\partial x^2} - k_c \bar{c}_Q \quad (\text{A4b})$$

$c_{P,t=0} = c_P^*$ (the total bulk concentration of adsorbate $c_A^* + c_B^*$) and $c_{Q,t=0} = 0$.

The general solutions of equations (A3) are:

$$\bar{c}_P = P_1 \exp \left[\left(\frac{s}{D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} x \right] + P_2 \exp \left[- \left(\frac{s}{D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} x \right] + \frac{c_P^*}{s} \quad (\text{A5a})$$

$$\bar{c}_Q = Q_1 \exp \left[\left(\frac{s + k_c}{D} \right)^{1/2} x \right] + Q_2 \exp \left[- \left(\frac{s + k_c}{D} \right)^{1/2} x \right] \quad (\text{A5b})$$

The integration constants, P_1, P_2, Q_1 and Q_2 are obtained from the semi-infinite and surface conditions:

$$x = \infty \begin{cases} c_P = c_P^* \rightarrow P_1 = 0 \\ c_Q = 0 \rightarrow Q_1 = 0 \end{cases} x$$

$$= 0 \begin{cases} \left(\frac{\partial \bar{c}_P}{\partial x} \right)_{x=0} = \left(\frac{\partial \bar{c}_A}{\partial x} \right)_{x=0} = \bar{v}_{ad} \rightarrow P_2 = -\bar{v}_{ad} \left(\frac{s}{D} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \\ \left(\frac{\partial \bar{c}_Q}{\partial x} \right)_{x=0} = - \left(\frac{\partial \bar{c}_A}{\partial x} \right)_{x=0} = -\bar{v}_{ad} \rightarrow Q_2 = \bar{v}_{ad} \left(\frac{s + k_c}{D} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \end{cases}$$

Then, the particular solutions become:

$$\bar{c}_{P(x=0)} = -\bar{v}_{ad} \left(\frac{s}{D} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} + c_P^* \quad (\text{A6a})$$

$$\bar{c}_{Q(x=0)} = \bar{v}_{ad} \left(\frac{s + k_c}{D} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (\text{A6b})$$

Reverting the variables change it is possible to obtain the expression for $\Delta c_{A,x=0}$:

$$\overline{\Delta c_{A(x=0)}} = -\overline{\Delta v_{ad}} \left[\frac{K_1}{K_1 + 1} \left(\frac{S}{D} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{K_1 + 1} \left(\frac{S + k_c}{D} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right] \quad (\text{A7})$$